

Spatial Patterns in Scientific Production: Evidence from Brazil

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Abstract

Spatial scientometrics enhances the understanding of the global distribution and impact of scientific production, thereby guiding strategic decision-making and resource allocation for scientific and technological advancement. This study examines Brazilian scientific collaboration networks from 2010 to 2019, analyzing factors related to geographical and institutional proximities using the Lattes Platform. Starting with a database of 232,966 Ph.D. holders, we found that 105 municipalities accounted for over 80% of research collaborations, which represents approximately 2% of the total municipalities in Brazil. The effect of geographical distance on scientific collaboration was assessed using gravity model of spatial interaction and count data. The results indicated an average decrease of 9.2% in national collaboration for every 100 km of distance between researchers.

1. Introduction

There has been a global increase in collaborative research across all fields (Glänzel & Schubert, 2004; Sidone, 2018). However, significant differences remain in the number of co-authors, publication frequency, and reference lists (Elsevier, 2018). As networks of collaboration intensified toward the end of the 20th century, the Royal Society (2011) estimated that more than one-third of global scientific output resulted from collaborations involving more than one author. It is important to note, however, that Brazil, China, Turkey, Taiwan, India, and South Korea produced 70% of their publications without international collaboration.

Among the themes comprising the research agenda for scientific collaborations in Brazil, the study by McManus et al. (2020) is noteworthy. The authors identified beneficial effects for all parties involved in international collaborations and argued that Brazilian researchers, particularly those in the fields of Life and Exact Sciences, make significant contributions to networks that are geographically distant. They recommended that future studies explore the networks of Brazilian researchers to gain a more comprehensive understanding. To address the research gap identified by McManus et al. (2020), this study aims to enhance the understanding of collaboration networks in Brazil, considering that the country is one of the most productive nations globally. To achieve this, the network of Brazilian researchers will be constructed based on information extracted from the Lattes Platform (CNPq). We test

geographical and institutional proximities to determine their impact on the probability of national collaboration.

In the literature, it is well-established that countries with extensive territorial dimensions tend to foster greater national collaboration, while smaller nations are more inclined to engage in international partnerships (Davidson Frame & Carpenter, 1979; Royal Society, 2011; Sidone, 2018). As the accelerated growth of scientific production in emerging countries, such as Brazil, is more attributed to national rather than international collaboration (Sidone, 2018), the following research problem arises: To what extent may the different types of proximity affect the flow of scientific knowledge in Brazil?

This study is organized into four main sections following this introduction: first, a theoretical framework is outlined; next, the ‘materials and methods’ section describes the data and empirical model used; subsequently, the results are presented; and finally, the discussion and conclusion provide insights of the findings.

2. Literature background

Local knowledge flows play a crucial role in interactive learning (Gertler, 2003; Glaeser et al., 1992; Storper & Venables, 2004). However, the literature also emphasizes that geographical proximity is not a sufficient condition for fostering interactive learning and innovation, as physical distance alone cannot stimulate interaction among local actors (Boschma, 2005; Broekel, 2015). In this regard, we draw on Boschma's discussion of the dimensions of proximity, particularly geographical and institutional aspects.

In Brazil, 95% of scientific research is conducted within graduate programs, particularly those affiliated with public universities, according to estimates by McManus et al. (2020). Brazilian public universities are responsible for the majority of scientific articles indexed in research databases, and the concentration of knowledge in the country can be attributed to the geographical locations of their campuses, which exhibit patterns similar to those of other developing nations (Leta et al., 2006; Sidone, 2018). In this study, we consider the headquarter campus to compute institutional proximity (78 were identified). If two regions both host a headquarter campus, they are considered institutionally proximate; otherwise, they are institutionally distant. This approach is justified as the main campuses encompass most of the research attributes associated with the universities, aligning with the methodology outlined by Sidone et al. (2016). This research is warranted because, despite a process of deconcentration in Brazilian scientific production (Sidone et al., 2016), Brazil still exhibits lower levels of international collaboration compared to its neighboring countries (Glänzel & Schubert, 2005; Sidone, 2018).

There has been a growing interest in empirical studies conducted in countries that exhibit increased levels of national collaboration, such as Brazil (Haddad et al., 2017; Sidone et al., 2016), China (Wang et al., 2005), Turkey (Gossart & Özman, 2009), and Finland (Puuska et al., 2014). In this context, scientific collaboration networks can be analyzed using graphs theory, where researchers are represented as nodes and co-authorships as edges (Chen et al., 2019; Ye et al., 2008). Additionally, geographical and spatial effects can be considered (Acosta et al., 2011; Katz, 1994; Scherngell & Hu, 2011; Sidone et al., 2016).

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Data description

Curriculum Vitae (CV) for undergraduate, master's, and Ph.D. holders in Brazil can be accessed through the Lattes Platform (<http://lattes.cnpq.br>). This national system manages information about researchers and their scientific activities. Lane (2010) highlighted best practices for the Lattes Platform, arguing that it creates appropriate incentives for researchers and academic institutions to utilize the database effectively. Data collection began with the identification of the CVs of all Ph.D. holders registered on the Lattes Platform. From each CV, information regarding publications in the category of journal articles was extracted. Based on ScriptLattes (Mena-Chalco & Cesar Junior, 2009), co-authorships for all publications by each Ph.D. holder were identified, enabling the mapping of collaborations strictly among researchers registered on the Lattes Platform. The data were organized by year, thereby generating a co-authorship network for each individual year.

These procedures enable the identification of academic publications, Lattes IDs (comprising 16 digits), professional addresses of researchers, and additional information regarding Brazilian scientific production. The aggregation of geographical units is a common practice in spatial scientometrics (Frenken et al., 2009), enabling the use of cities as nodes in collaborative networks (Pan et al., 2012). In this study, we utilized both professional addresses and Lattes IDs as proxies to identify Ph.D. holders, adhering to the methodology outlined by Sidone et al. (2016).

After identifying co-authors, we employed the full-counting method, in which each author or region is credited with one unit of collaboration for their contributions to publications. Consequently, we adjusted our data to align with the specifications of the model (Scherngell & Barber, 2011). Thus, we utilized count data models to estimate the effect of geographical distance on the probability of national collaboration between 2010 and 2019, extending the period analyzed by Sidone et al. (2016).

The initial database consisted of 232,966 active Ph.D. holders, defined as individuals who had publications registered in the three years preceding the data collection in 2020. We analyzed eight major fields of knowledge according to the Lattes Platform: i) Agricultural Sciences; ii) Human Sciences; iii) Biological Sciences; iv) Health Sciences; v) Engineering; vi) Applied Social Sciences; vii) Exact and Earth Sciences; and viii) Linguistics, Letters, and Arts. One method for representing graphs is through adjacency matrices. These matrices are square, with rows and columns corresponding to the nodes of the network. Scientific collaboration networks, which are undirected graphs with weighted edges, can be effectively represented using adjacency matrices, where the weights indicate the strength of collaboration between researchers (Newman, 2001). To construct the matrix of inter-municipal co-authorships by field of knowledge, we associated researchers, municipalities, and the major areas of knowledge reported in each curriculum vitae (CV).

3.2 Empirical model

Statistical regressions enable the use of scientific collaborations as the dependent variable, with dimensions of proximity serving as independent variables (Hoekman et al., 2009; Ponds et al., 2007). Spatial interaction models describe functions that characterize the origin i and

destination j of interactions, as well as the separation between two regions, i e j . The general model is represented by the following equation:

$$Y_{ij} = X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Y_{ij} represents the stochastic collaboration flow between two regions, i and j ($y_{ij} \geq 0$). X_{ij} function captures the stochastic relationship with random variables. ε_{ij} is the error term that varies across inter-regional pairs, i and j . X_{ij} corresponds to the general gravity model.

$$X_{ij} = O_i D_j S(u_{ij}); \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

The functions O_i e D_j characterize the interactions of regions origin i and destination j , which can be described by *power functions* in accordance with classical spatial interaction theory (Sen & Smith, 1995). The specification of spatial separation term $S(u_{ij})$ occurs in the multivariate exponential function form, allowing for other dimensions of proximity to be included in the model simultaneously. Hence, the functions take the following forms:

$$O_i = O(o_i, \alpha_1) = o_i^{\alpha_1}; \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$D_j = D(d_j, \alpha_2) = d_j^{\alpha_2}; \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

$$S(u_{ij}) = S(u_{ij}, \beta) = \exp\left[\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}\right]; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

The variables o_i and d_j measure characteristics of regions, i and j . The variable $u_{ij}^{(k)}$ represents k measures of spatial separation between these regions. The term β_k refers to the set of k unknown parameters associated with each of the k measures of spatial separation between these regions. Since the scientific interactions among municipalities are represented as undirected graphs, the variables of origin and destination are symmetrical ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$). Therefore, it is expected that the estimates of these mass terms will be close to unity and statistically significant. We obtained the following empirical model to be estimated by replacing equations in the initial model:

$$Y_{ij} = \alpha + o_i^{\alpha_1} d_j^{\alpha_2} \exp\left[\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}\right] + \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

The variables of origin (o_i) and destination (d_j) are measured by the total number of scientific publications in each municipality. It is assumed that collaborations among municipalities positively depend on total number of publications in each of them. We used two parameters for separating variables. The first one (β_1) consists of a matrix of geographical distance in which every element $u_{ij}^{(1)}$ is calculated by distance in kilometres (km) between two municipalities, i and j . To calculate the distance in kilometers (km), we used the H3 geospatial indexing system in the Python language. It is a discrete global grid system composed of hexagonal tiles with hierarchical indexes, as discussed by Brodsky (2020). The second parameter (β_2) was used to measure the institutional proximity among municipalities. We constructed an institutional matrix for municipalities, assigning $u_{ij}^{(2)} = 1$ for municipalities i and j when both have headquartered campus, and $u_{ij}^{(2)} = 0$ otherwise.

Count data models are useful for addressing specification problems in spatial interaction models, as opposed to the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method (Long & Freese, 2001). The specification problem can be mitigated by interpreting the model as a count data model, which

assumes that the data-generating process produces only non-negative integers. The number of scientific collaborations may follow a Poisson distribution, as expressed in the following equation:

$$\Pr(Y_{ij}=y_{ij} | X_{ij}) = \frac{e^{-\mu_{ij}} \cdot \mu_{ij}^{y_{ij}}}{y_{ij}!} \quad ; i, j = 1, \dots, n; \quad y_{ij} = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (7)$$

Where μ_{ij} is the set of independent variables in the empirical model (6):

$$\mu_{ij} = X_{ij} = \exp [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log(o_i) + \alpha_2 \log(d_j) + [\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}]] \quad (8)$$

The negative binomial distribution is a widely used alternative to empirical studies of scientific collaboration (Hoekman et al., 2009; Sidone et al., 2016). It accounts for unobserved heterogeneity by introducing an additional parameter. The negative binomial density function (Equation 9) and the conditional variance (Equation 10) are expressed by the following equations:

$$\Pr(Y_{ij}=y_{ij} | X_{ij}) = \frac{\Gamma(y_{ij} + \alpha^{-1})}{y_{ij}! \Gamma(\alpha^{-1})} \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha^{-1}}{\alpha^{-1} + \mu_{ij}}\right)^{\alpha^{-1}} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{ij}}{\alpha^{-1} + \mu_{ij}}\right)^{y_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

$$V[Y_{ij}|X_{ij}] = \mu_{ij} + \alpha \mu_{ij}^2; \quad \mu_{ij} = E[Y_{ij}|X_{ij}] \quad (10)$$

Where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, and α is the heterogeneity parameter.

Upon associating researchers with geographical units, the adjacency matrix is constructed from the total number of inter-municipal collaborations between geographical units, while the main diagonal of the matrix represents the total number of intra-municipal collaborations. Inter-municipal distances $u_{ij}^{(1)}$ were measured in kilometers (km), and intra-municipal distances $u_{ii}^{(1)}$ follow the method proposed by Bröcker (1988): $\left(\frac{2}{3}\right) \left(\frac{A}{\pi}\right)^{0.5}$.

4. Results

To establish a network of inter-municipal collaborations, we began with a sample of 232,966 Ph.D. holders distributed across 3,187 municipalities. However, 51,155 of these individuals did not provide their professional addresses, and only 173,584 disclosed both their professional addresses and primary research areas on the Lattes Platform. After assessing the presence of collaborative pairs, we identified 136,939 active researchers across 1,271 municipalities. We recorded a total of 1,636,031 publications, of which only 694,159 had more than one co-author. The total number of publications featuring at least two active researchers was 602,170, resulting in a cumulative total of 2,590,497 collaborations. The breakdown of collaborations is as follows: 2010-2011 (349,454), 2012-2013 (489,781), 2014-2015 (559,295), 2016-2017 (581,904), and 2018-2019 (610,063).

Scientific production is concentrated in 105 municipalities, which account for 2,090,404 collaborations (80.69%). This includes 969,512 inter-municipal collaborations and 1,120,892 intra-municipal collaborations. This concentration represents 2% of the total number of municipalities in Brazil, which has 5,572 municipalities according to the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (2021). The regional clusters are summarized in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scientific production in 105 municipalities

Although the edges connect various regions of the country, the most intense collaborations originate from Southern and Southeastern Brazil. Figure 2 illustrates the main collaborations in a graph.

Figure 2. Weighted graphs of scientific collaborations

The effects of physical distance on inter-municipal collaborations have decreased from 2010 to 2019. Figure 3 reveals that, on average, researchers increasingly engage in more distant collaborations.

Figure 3. Inter-municipal collaborations in kilometres (2010-2019)

However, the major areas of knowledge on the Lattes Platform enable various patterns of inter-municipal collaborations. For example, biological sciences show a growing trend, while engineering has reduced its average intermunicipal collaborations.

Biological Sciences

Engineering

Figure 4. Average distance of inter-municipal collaboration in kilometres

In terms of the number of collaborations, Agricultural Sciences remained steady, while Exact and Earth Sciences, Biological Sciences, and Health Sciences achieved the highest number of collaborations with an increasing trend. Among the fields, Linguistics, Letters and Arts, Applied Social Sciences, and Human Sciences showed the lowest number of collaborations, with Engineering following closely behind.

Figure 5. Collaborations in eight major areas of knowledge of the Lattes Platform

We also found that the increasing distance between two researchers decreases the probability of both intra- and inter-municipal collaboration, as indicated by the count data models presented in Table 1 for 105 municipalities.

Table 1. Count data models for *intra* and *inter-municipal* collaborations (2010-2019)

Model	Variables	Results
Poisson	Origin-destination ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$)	.7081669 *** (.0005792)
	Geographical Distance (β_1)	-.0021057 *** (1.91e-06)
	Institutional Proximity (β_2)	.9028553 *** (.0017975)
	Constant	-8.540414 *** (.0086653)
Negative Binomial	Origin-destination ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$)	.7067676 *** (.0165461)
	Geographical Distance (β_1)	- .0009677 *** (.0000149)
	Institutional Proximity (β_2)	.6407419 *** (.0393409)
	Constant	-7.470103 *** (.2186921)
	Heterogeneity (α)	1.49499 *** (.0256107)

Note: n=5.209; Parentheses indicate standard errors; *** corresponds to statistical significance levels of 0.001.

All results were statistically significant. The parameter representing geographical distance was negative in both the Poisson and Negative Binomial models, suggesting that increased collaboration is associated with decreased geographical distance. Conversely, the parameter for institutional distance was positive in both models, indicating that greater scientific collaboration is linked to closer institutional proximity. The estimates for the mass terms (origin α_1 and destination α_2) were statistically significant and close to unit. Overall, the Negative Binomial model performed better, as it effectively captured heterogeneity with a parameter $\alpha = 1.51$. The negative binomial parameter indicates that an increase in distance of 100 km between two researchers reduces the probability of collaboration by an average of 9.2%, *ceteris paribus*. The interpretation of these results is discussed by Long and Freese (2001, p. 491).

5. Discussion and Conclusion

This study aimed to enhance the understanding of scientific collaboration networks in Brazil by analyzing geographical effects from 2010 to 2019. Computational methods facilitated the extraction of data directly from the Lattes Platform (CNPq), enabling the mapping of a collaborative network comprising 136,939 Ph.D. holders distributed across 1,271 Brazilian municipalities. We established pairs of municipalities using adjacency matrices to analyze the

intensity of collaborative networks and to test the probability of collaborations based on geographical distance.

The analysis revealed a continuous increase in total scientific collaborations over each biennium (see Figure 5). The results revealed a trend of total inter-municipal scientific collaborations occurring over increasingly greater distances, on average (see Figure 3). However, the fields of knowledge exhibit different behaviors (see Figure 4). McManus et al. (2020) identified that Brazilian researchers in the fields of Life and Exact Sciences significantly contribute to networks that are geographically distant rather than local. Indeed, this study demonstrated that Biological Sciences engage in collaborations with more distant national networks. However, we did not observe this trend in the field of Engineering.

Global scientific production is characterized by a process of geographical deconcentration, although global cities appear to benefit from international competition (Grossetti et al., 2012). Sidone et al. (2016) provided evidence of this deconcentration process in Brazilian scientific production from 1992 to 2009, which included municipalities with lower levels of scientific output. The authors did not find evidence that the impact of geographic distance diminished over time. In a similar vein, our analysis revealed a concentration of Ph.D. holders across 105 municipalities after mapping the network from 2010 to 2019.

The model's parameters indicate that increased scientific collaboration is associated with shorter geographical distances and closer institutional proximity. The negative binomial model revealed that, on average, there is a 9.1% reduction in national collaboration for every 100 kilometers of distance between two Ph.D. holders in Brazil, while holding other variables constant (see Table 1). Although geography is not the sole factor influencing interactions among researchers, physical distance still plays a significant role in shaping networks of scientific collaboration in Brazil. This conclusion aligns with the findings of Sidone et al. (2016) in the Brazilian context and Hoekman et al. (2010) in the European context. Future studies could focus on other dimensions of proximity, including cognitive, organizational, and social aspects. Additionally, key control variables may be included, such as regional economic levels, innovation levels, and the number of researchers. These results have important implications, as they facilitate the evaluation of the effectiveness of regional policies and help identify scientific advancements in regions with limited resources.

Author contributions

Luís Fabiano Farias Borges: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing—original draft. Jesús Mena-Chalco: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing—review & editing. Bruno Brandão Fischer: Formal analysis, Methodology, Writing—review & editing.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests.

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